

Simulation of snake-like swimming system using granular model

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Abstract. Spherical grains connected with springs are proposed as model for simulating a snake-like swimming system. Instead of changing position of the grains, normal length of each spring is modulated to mimic contraction and relaxation of muscles between bones, which then introduce grains configuration of the system. Molecular dynamics method implementing Euler algorithm is used to calculate interaction between grains and also how grains are influenced by its environment, i.e. water, that push the system into a certain direction. Buoyant force and gravitational force are considered to be equal to simplify the system. Then, only viscous and spring forces are used for the simulation. Spring force will change grains configuration in the system, while viscous force will perform action by pushing the water in order for the system to move as reaction of the action. Sinusoidal relation between springs length, i.e. the muscles, is proposed since there is no available information for contraction and relaxation of the muscles. Sort of directional motion can be obtained but not yet efficient.

Key words: Granular model, molecular dynamics, snake-like swimming system, sinusoidal pattern

INTRODUCTION

Swimming of long and narrow animal has been studied and analyzed more than fifty years ago (Taylor 1952), which later can be differentiated into surface and subsurface modes of swimming (Graham et al. 1987), or into constricting and nonconstricting colubrid (Jayne 1985). Illustration of a sea snake swim down in the sea is shown in figure 1 (BlueWorldTV, 2014), while Figure 2 shows simultaneous lateral and dorsal views of Swimming juvenile *Nerodia s. sipedon* (Jayne 1985).

Figure 1: Swimming down of sea snake as documented by BlueWorldTV (2014) at time: (a) 10:58, (b) 10:59, (c) 11:00, and (d) 11:01.

Figure 2: Swimming juvenile *Nerodia s. sipedon* (Jayne 1985): simultaneous lateral and dorsal views.

Both previous figures show that snake swimming is actually a three-dimensional movement, where the snake can also manipulate its density to help it floats or sinks while swimming.

Figure 3: Swimming pattern of: (a) *Natrix natrix*, (b) *N. natrix*, (c) *Nerodia fasciata*, and (d) *Anguilla* as collected in (Graham et al. 1987).

In order to have a propulsion from the surrounding water by changing its curved body different snake uses different pattern, where some of the patterns are shown in figure 3. None of them is in pure sinusoidal form.

No longer than ten years ago a snake-like swimming robot has been developed using Ionic Polymer-Metal Composite (IPMC) actuator and sensor and also simulated using input-output data as a linear time invariant (LTI) system (Kamamichi et al. 2006). Later on it is also optimized using the biological concept of central pattern generators (CPGs) in the locomotion controller (Crespi & Ijspeert 2008).

Figure 4. The swimming snake-robot using CPGs in its locomotion controller (Crespi & Ijspeert 2008).

In this work the snake-like swimming system is simulated using granular model whose individual spherical grain drag coefficient can be altered (Nuraini *et al.*, 2017) in order to produce directional motion for the system. There are N identical spherical grains with density ρ_g (less than water density ρ_f), where grains i and $i+1$ are connected with linear spring with constant $k_{1,i}$ and length $l_{1,i}$, but grains i and $i+2$ are connected with linear spring with constant $k_{2,i}$ and $l_{2,i}$. Both springs length is function of time, $l_{1,i} = l_{1,i}(t)$ and $l_{2,i} = l_{2,i}(t)$, but with different phase producing right pattern for optimal propulsion. Average forward velocity for several different patterns are analyzed and compared, where sinusoidal pattern are among them. Influence of wavelength λ , frequency f , and amplitude A is also discussed.

2 Model

Simulation system consists of N spherical grains with identical diameter D connected with spring with spring constants k and length l as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Chain of spherical granular particles for modeling floating biomechanical system with view in: (a) xy plane and (b) xz plane.

Grain i will interact with other four grain, grains $i-2$, $i-1$, $i+1$ and $i+2$ through spring force

$$\vec{F}_{ij}^s = -k(l_{ij} - r_{ij})\hat{r}_{ij}, \quad (1)$$

with j could be $i-2$, $i-1$, $i+1$ or $i+2$ and

$$\vec{r}_{ij} = \vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j, \quad (2)$$

$$r_{ij} = |\vec{r}_{ij}| = \sqrt{\vec{r}_{ij} \cdot \vec{r}_{ij}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{r}_{ij} = \frac{\vec{r}_{ij}}{r_{ij}}. \quad (4)$$

With the environment every grain will interact through viscous force

$$\vec{F}_i^\eta = -3\pi\eta_f D_i (\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_f) \quad (5)$$

where η_f , D_i , and \vec{v}_f stand for fluid viscosity, spherical grain diameter, and fluid velocity. Equations (1) and (2) mostly affect motion of the system in horizontal direction if it moves only in xy plan. There are also two remaining forces, which are in vertical direction. The first is gravitational force

$$\vec{F}_i^g = -\frac{1}{6}\pi\rho_b D_i^3 \vec{g} \quad (6)$$

and the second is buoyant force (Viridi et al. 2018)

$$\vec{F}_i^\rho = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{6}\pi D_i^3 \rho_f \vec{g}, & z \leq z_f - \frac{1}{2}D_i, \\ \pi \left\{ \frac{1}{4}D_i^2 \left[(z_f - z) + \frac{1}{2}D_i \right] - \frac{1}{3} \left[(z_f - z)^3 + \frac{1}{8}D_i^3 \right] \right\} \rho_f \vec{g}, & z_f + \frac{1}{2}D_i \leq z \leq z_f - \frac{1}{2}D_i, \\ 0, & z_f + \frac{1}{2}D_i \leq z. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

which can accommodate if only partially immersed in water, where z_f is position of water surface. Using Equations (1), (5)–(7), grain acceleration at time t can be calculated through Newton's second law of motion

$$\vec{a}_i = \frac{1}{m_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\vec{F}_i^\eta + \vec{F}_i^g + \vec{F}_i^\rho + \sum_{j>i} \vec{F}_{ij}^s \right), \quad (8)$$

and then velocity at time $t + \Delta t$ from Euler algorithm is

$$\vec{v}(t + \Delta t) = \vec{v}(t) + \vec{a}_i \Delta t, \quad (9)$$

so is position at time $t + \Delta t$

$$\vec{r}(t + \Delta t) = \vec{r}(t) + \vec{v}(t) \Delta t, \quad (10)$$

iterated from $t = t_{\text{beg}}$ until $t = t_{\text{end}}$ with time step Δt . In each iteration step system center of mass can be calculated through

$$x_{\text{com}} = \frac{1}{M} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N m_i \vec{r}_i \right) \cdot \hat{i}, \quad (11)$$

$$y_{\text{com}} = \frac{1}{M} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N m_i \vec{r}_i \right) \cdot \hat{j}, \quad (12)$$

$$z_{\text{com}} = \frac{1}{M} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N m_i \vec{r}_i \right) \cdot \hat{k}, \quad (13)$$

with

$$M = \sum_{i=1}^N m_i. \quad (14)$$

And the displacement is simply calculated using

$$\Delta x = x_{\text{com}}(t_{\text{end}}) - x_{\text{com}}(t_{\text{beg}}), \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta y = y_{\text{com}}(t_{\text{end}}) - y_{\text{com}}(t_{\text{beg}}), \quad (16)$$

and

$$\Delta r = \sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta y)^2}. \quad (17)$$

For simplicity it is assumed that there is no motion in z direction, which can be set if $d\rho_f/dt = 0$, $d\rho_b/dt = 0$, and Equations (1) and (5) only in xy plan. How to change l_{ij} is the most important part in this work, which is assumed to be

$$l_{ij}(t + \Delta t) = l_{ij}(t) + A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t\right), \quad (18)$$

where A and T are defined as muscle modulation amplitude and period. We also propose another mechanism, where the change of spring length also depends on grain position, such as

$$l_{ij}(t + \Delta t) = l_{ij}(t) + A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t\right) \left(1 - \left|\frac{N/2 - N}{N}\right|\right), \quad (19)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work modulation amplitude A and period T are varied to obtain higher value of displacement. Other parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
N	20	-
g	10	m/s^2
ρ_f	1000	kg/m^3
η_f	0.01	$\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
ρ_b	500	kg/m^3
D_b	0.025	m
A	$(1 - 10) \times 10^{-5}$	m
T	1 - 10	s

Table 2: Grains initial positions

i	x	y	z
1	0.10	0.469	0
2	0.13	0.506	0
3	0.15	0.531	0
4	0.17	0.554	0
5	0.20	0.581	0
6	0.23	0.597	0
7	0.25	0.600	0
8	0.28	0.593	0
9	0.30	0.581	0
10	0.33	0.554	0
11	0.35	0.531	0

i	x	y	z
12	0.38	0.494	0
13	0.40	0.469	0
14	0.43	0.436	0
15	0.45	0.419	0
16	0.48	0.403	0
17	0.50	0.400	0
18	0.53	0.407	0
19	0.55	0.419	0
20	0.57	0.436	0
21	0.60	0.469	0

3.1 Grains configuration evolution

Using default parameters given in Table 1 and particles initials position in Table 2, following typical grains configuration is obtained as shown in figure 6, which uses Equation (18).

Figure 6: Typical evolution of system configuration for time t : (a) 0, (b) 1.1, (c) 1.7, (d) 2.5, (e) 3.3, (f) 4, (g) 4.6, (h) 5.1 s.

It is not so similar compared to reported one (Crespi & Ijspeert 2008).

3.2 Period variation

Final grains configuration for different modulation period T is given in fig 7 and produced displacements is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7: System displacement Δx , Δy (left) and Δr (right) for $N = 20$ and $A = 10^{-5}$ m, as function of modulation period T : (a) 1 s, (b) 2 s, (c) 3 s, (d) 4 s, (e) 5 s, (f) 6 s, (g) 7 s, (h) 8 s, (i) 9 s, and (j) 10 s.

Figure 8: System displacement Δx , Δy (left) and Δr (right) for $N = 20$ and $A = 10^{-5}$ m, as function of modulation period T .

3.3 Amplitude variation

Final grains configuration for different modulation amplitude A is given in fig 9 and produced displacements is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: System displacement Δx , Δy (left) and Δr (right) for $N = 20$ and $T = 1$ s, as function of modulation amplitude A : (a) 1, (b) 2, (c) 3, (d) 4, (e) 5, (f) 6, (g) 7, (h) 8, (i) 9, and (j) 10×10^{-5} m.

Figure 10: System displacement Δx , Δy (left) and Δr (right) for $N = 20$ and $T = 1$ s, as function of modulation period T .

3.4 Not homogen muscle length modulation

Using Equation (19) different result is obtained as shown in Figure 11, which is still not similar to observed in experiment (Crespi & Ijspeert 2008), but it is already better compared to Figure 6.

Figure 11: Evolution of system configuration with inhomogeneous muscle modulation for time t : (a) 4.4, (b) 5.3, (c) 5.9, (d) 6.3, (e) 7.7, (f) 8.3, (g) 9.3, (h) 10.4 s.

Simulation of snake-like swimming system using granular model has been performed. Directional motion can be achieved but not efficient compared to experiment result based on CPGs. Information generated from CPGs could be used to test the simulation system. Introducing inhomogenous muscle modulation makes grains configuration better but not yet similar to reported experiment results.

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